

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, CA 95814

In Reply Refer to:
2022-0070999-S7-001

November 5, 2024

J. Stephen Volk
Environmental Division Chief
Military Ocean Terminal Concord
Department of the Army
Military Surface Deployment and Distribution Command
834th Transportation Battalion
410 Norman Ave
Concord, CA 94520-1142

Subject: Programmatic Formal Consultation for the Department of the Army's Military Ocean Terminal Concord Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan, Programs, and Projects for 2023-2028, Contra Costa County, California

Dear Mr. Volk:

This letter is in response to the Department of the Army's (Army) December 14, 2023, letter requesting formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO) Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) Management Programs and Projects in Contra Costa County, California. The Army determined that INRMP covered activities may affect and are likely to adversely affect the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris raviventris*) (SMHM) and the endangered California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) (CRR). The Army also determined that INRMP activities may affect, but are not likely to adversely affect the threatened central California distinct population segment (DPS) of the California tiger salamander (*Ambystoma californiense*) (CTS), the threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*) (CRLF), and the endangered soft bird's-beak (*Cordylanthus mollis* ssp. *mollis*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In reviewing this proposed project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Army's December 14, 2023, letter requesting consultation; (2) the December 14, 2023, *Programmatic Biological Assessment Description of Proposed Action - MOTCO Integrated Natural Resource Management Plan Management Programs and Projects* (BA) prepared by Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC; (3) the June 2023 *Final Military Ocean Terminal Concord Integrated Natural*

Resources Management Plan; (4) several emails, video meetings, and telephone conversations between the Service and the Army from April 21, 2022 to September 24, 2024; and (5) other information available to the Service.

The Army has requested consultation for implementation of the 2023-2028 INRMP. Although the Army has not initiated consultation for previous iterations of their INRMP at MOTCO, the Army and the Service agreed programmatic consultation is appropriate moving forward. Programmatic consultation, as defined in 50 CFR 402.02, is a consultation addressing an agency's multiple actions on a program, region, or other basis. Programmatic consultations allow the Service and the National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) to consult on the effects of programmatic actions such as: (1) multiple similar, frequently occurring, or routine actions expected to be implemented in particular geographic areas; and (2) a proposed program, plan, policy, or regulation providing a framework for future proposed actions. The Service has determined the implementation of the INRMP presents as a program of routine actions. Individual projects determined inconsistent with this programmatic informal concurrence and programmatic biological opinion (PBO) are those that exceed the effects analyzed and therefore would require a separate consultation.

California Tiger Salamander and California Red-legged Frog

Potential CTS and CRLF breeding habitat occurs within the MOTCO INRMP coverage area and consists of freshwater ponds and stock ponds. Potential dispersal and aestivation habitat is located in the non-native grassland habitats nearby.

During the 1998-1999 surveys in support of a previous INRMP (Downard *et al.* 1999), CTS were found at nine different locations and CRLF were found at ten different locations, but all were within portions of the Inland Area that are no longer part of MOTCO. These locations range in distance from 4 to 6 miles from the current installation boundary, and California Highway 4 represents an obstacle to any potential northward movement. However, these species may be using any of the several springs in the Los Medanos Hills on-site as breeding pools. Tadpoles of an unknown species (not CTS larvae) were observed in at least one of these during the reconnaissance surveys conducted in June 2009.

In recent years, in accordance with the Act and as part of the Service's coordination under the Sikes Act in support of previous INRMPs, the Service required the Army to complete protocol-level surveys for the CTS and CRLF because the current MOTCO boundary remains within the range of the central California DPS of CTS and the CRLF, suitable habitat occurs within this current boundary, and potential dispersal and aestivation habitat is located in the non-native grassland habitats nearby. Protocol-level surveys of potential CTS and CRLF habitat within the coverage area are conducted annually. Protocol-level surveys were completed during the 2014-2015, 2015-2016, 2017-2018, and 2019-2020 breeding seasons. These surveys, in conjunction with past surveys, indicate a negative finding for CTS and CRLF within current potential habitat on MOTCO (Eco & Associates 2021).

Despite having both suitable aquatic wetland and suitable upland habitats available for the CTS and CRLF to utilize, no CTS or CRLF have been documented within the current boundary of MOTCO and as mentioned previously, California Highway 4 likely represents a barrier to immigration of CTS or CRLF into MOTCO from the nearest known extant populations south of

Highway 4. However, MOTCO proposes to continue protocol-level special status reptile and amphibian surveys as part of the covered activities for the INRMP. These include the continued protocol-level surveys for CTS and CRLF. These specific surveys are for the sole purpose of informing the Service for recovery of these species. As such, a Service-approved biologist holding a 10(a)(1)(A) recovery permit will conduct the appropriate surveys with take for CTS and CRLF authorized through issuance of the recovery permit. Future surveys will be evaluated for need based on continued non-detection, or depending on a positive survey result, reinitiation of this consultation may be appropriate.

In the unlikely event that a CTS or CRLF is detected during non-CTS or CRLF special status surveys or INRMP covered activities, the Army is proposing several conservation measures such as the employment of a Service-approved biologist with several planning, monitoring, surveying, and species conservation responsibilities such as the authority to stop proposed activities and evaluate/execute avoidance and minimization measures should they be warranted (please refer to the BA for the full description of the Service-approved biologist authority and responsibilities and a full list of general biological conservation measures proposed for INRMP covered activities). The Army is also proposing avoidance measures such as work stoppage and the observation of a work window for CTS and CRLF (May 1 to October 31) which avoids the CTS and CRLF breeding season.

The Service concurs with the Army's determination that the proposed project is not likely adversely affect the CTS and CRLF based on the lack of occurrences over several decades and the implementation of conservation and avoidance measures.

Soft Bird's-beak

Two small populations of soft bird's-beak were observed at various locations within the Tidal Area during the University of Arizona surveys in 1998-1999 (Downard *et al.* 1999), including populations in Middle Point Marsh and Hasting's Slough West Marsh. Soft bird's-beak was also found during recent rare plant surveys conducted in 2019 within the wetlands of the Tidal Area (Eco & Associates 2019). Specifically, this species was observed at two locations, in the pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*)-dominated marshes west of the chemical plant and east of the easternmost pier, and generally occurs in the salt marsh habitat in and around MOTCO.

Although soft bird's-beak is known to occur on MOTCO, the Army is proposing to implement avoidance measures that would avoid the plant and avoid adverse measures associated with INRMP covered activities. If INRMP covered activities or special status plant work activities are proposed in habitat that has not been surveyed within the 5 years preceding construction, a pre-construction presence/absence survey must be conducted in the spring and summer immediately prior to project implementation. Rare plant surveys will be conducted by a qualified botanist, in accordance with all applicable survey guidelines including those published by the Service (Service 2000), California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) (CDFW 2018) and California Native Plant Society (CNPS) (CNPS 2001). If determined to be necessary, reference site surveys will be conducted to confirm plant phenology (flowering periods). If INRMP covered activities or special status plant work activities are conducted in the vicinity of soft bird's-beak, a 20-foot no-work buffer will be established around each occurrence of the species. The 20-foot no-work buffer will be marked by a Service-approved biologist with pin flags and

monitored intermittently throughout the work activities to ensure avoidance of the soft-bird's-beak.

The Service concurs with the Army's determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the soft bird's-beak based on the implementation of conservation and avoidance measures. If activities near known soft bird's-beak have the potential to affect hydrology or soil conditions, reinitiation of this consultation may be appropriate.

The remainder of this document represents the Service's programmatic biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the SMHM and CRR.

CONSULTATION HISTORY

July 23, 2021	The Service received the consultation request from the Army.
August 31, 2021	The Service met with the Army and its consultants to review the items in the BA and discuss the Army's determinations. The Service also informed the Army that surveys for delta smelt were unnecessary due to current survey efforts being conducted in the area by other agencies.
October 15, 2021	The Service discussed items from the August meeting via telephone with the Army's consultant regarding take exemption for activities associated with the proposed INRMP and previous MOTCO projects with existing consultations.
November 1, 2021	The Service received an updated section to the BA.
December 6, 2021	The Army submitted a revised BA for the Service to review.
March 14, 2022	The Service requested a meeting to discuss the BA review and the Army's determinations for listed species.
March 18, 2022	The Service requested and attended a meeting with the Army to discuss the updated section of the BA and additional items in the BA. The Service requested the Army resubmit its consultation request letter due to changes in proposals, decision agreements, recommendations, and changes in determinations for listed species.
April 21, 2022	The Army sent the Service an updated request for initiation of programmatic formal consultation.
August 8, 2022	The Army submitted the Integrated Pest Management Plan to the Service to be reviewed in conjunction with the INRMP covered activities.

August 10, 2022	The Army submitted a list of bird species specific surveys that will be conducted under INRMP covered activities.
August 11, 2022	The Service notified the Army that the INRMP was set to expire at the end of the calendar year and that the consultation would only be valid for the remainder of the calendar year. The Army responded that a new INRMP was set to signed for the next 5-year period. The Service requested to pause consultation until the new INRMP was approved and signed by the Service's Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office.
January 9, 2023	The Army through the Army Corps of Engineers (Corps) submitted the Draft INRMP for review with the Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office (SFWO) and the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office (BDFWO).
March 6, 2023	Both Service offices provided comments on the Draft INRMP.
August 21, 2023	The Corps sent the Final MOTCO INRMP for 2023-2028 signed by the SFWO and National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) to the BDFWO.
December 14, 2023	The Army, through the Corps, sent a revised consultation request letter along with the final updated BA.
June 12, 2024	The Army, through the Corps, submitted additional information with regard to restricted boundaries in the Suisun Bay in accordance with 33 CFR 334.1110.
August 28, 2024	The Service held an in-person meeting with the Army to discuss the INRMP PBO and relevant information regarding the recent listing of the longfin smelt (<i>Spirinchus thaleichthys</i>) distinct population segment as endangered. The Army determined implementation of the INRMP would not affect the longfin smelt and it is not discussed further.
September 24, 2024	The BDFWO held a teleconference meeting with the Army and the SFWO to discuss future annual reporting/meetings and each Service office's roles and responsibilities with regard to the MOTCO INRMP and facilitation of this PBO.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The INRMP for 2023 through 2028 identifies a total of 13 management programs. These programs include: Special Status Species, Land Management, Wetlands/shoreline Management,

Invasive Species Control and Management, Cantonment Area Wildlife Control, Water Quality and Erosion Management, Migratory Bird Management, Recreation Management, Wildland Fire Management, Grazing Lease Program, and Environmental Restoration, Data Management, and Training of Natural Resources and Personnel. Of these 13 programs, several programs including Recreation Management, Data Management, and Training of Natural Resources Personnel are not expected to result in any adverse effects to listed species as they do not involve physical actions within habitats or with species. Within the INRMP, there are projects identified for some of the management programs that may affect listed species, while others do not have currently identified projects, but are likely to have future projects with the potential to affect the SMHM and CRR.

The covered activities defined in this PBO include one or more Small-Scale Projects (SSPs) and/or Resource Management Programs (RMPs) and their associated Project Actions (PAs) and Best Management Practices (BMPs) that will be implemented to meet the Army's INRMP responsibilities. Ongoing RMPs and SSPs are conducted on a recurring basis and may have a consistent or regular affect to species. Discrete RMPs and SSPs, by contrast, are INRMP projects with variable impacts to species, which may not occur on a recurring or regular basis. Each RMP and SSP may involve implementation of one or more PAs that is required to complete the project. The PAs that are required to implement SSPs/RMPs will vary with project location and conditions. Not all SSPs/RMPs will require each of the PAs identified and determining which PAs will be required for a specific SSP/RMP will occur on a case-by-case basis.

The activities that are likely to adversely affect SMHM and CRR include RMPs and SSPs that must be implemented to successfully complete INRMP project goals (collectively described as Covered Activities). Examples of RMPs include special status species surveys, wetland delineations, invasive species surveys, and invasive species management; examples of SSPs include culvert maintenance, erosion control, sign installation and other small-scale operations and management tasks associated with existing facilities. Ongoing RMPs and SSPs are conducted on a recurring basis and may have a consistent or regular affect to these species. Discrete RMPs and SSPs, by contrast, are have variable impacts to these species and may not occur on a recurring or regular basis. Each PA will also have BMPs that will be implemented to avoid and/or minimize affects to species.

Covered Activities

The Covered Activities in this PBO include:

- Covered Activity 1: Special Status Species Programs
- Covered Activity 2: Wetland/Shoreline Management Programs
- Covered Activity 3: Invasive Species Control Programs and Projects
- Covered Activity 4: Wildlife Control Programs and Projects
- Covered Activity 5: Water Quality and Erosion Control Programs and Projects
- Covered Activity 6: Migratory Bird Management Programs and Projects
- Covered Activity 7: Environmental Restoration Programs and Projects

Covered Activity 1: Special Status Species Programs

- Surveys

To evaluate the presence of special status species at MOTCO, surveys must be conducted within the coverage area. The coverage area is defined as within the MOTCO boundary and within the appropriate habitats for a selected species. A Habitat Sampling Plan (HSP) was developed to provide details regarding the special status species surveys, data collection, and survey methods for the special status species programs. Information from the HSP was used to develop the RMPs/SSPs associated with this Covered Activity. Pedestrian and boat-based surveys will be conducted using the methods described in the 2020 HSP for MOTCO within the Tidal Area, Suisun Bay, and Offshore Islands. Special status species surveys will be conducted pursuant to applicable Service-approved survey protocols. As appropriate, biologists surveying for special status species will be approved by the Service and have appropriate endangered species recovery permit(s).

A total of 12 bird species will be the focus of the special status bird surveys (Table 1). Of these species, two are federally protected pursuant to the Act; these include the CRR, and the California least tern (*Sternula antillarum browni*, CLT). The Army determined implementation of the INRMP would not affect the CLT and is not discussed further. Depending on survey results, reinitiation of this consultation may be appropriate.

Table. 1 Bird Surveys– MOTCO Target Species

Scientific Name	Common Name	Survey Period
<i>Athene cunicularia</i>	California burrowing owl	Feb 1 - Aug 31
<i>Bubo virginianus</i>	great horned owl	April 15 - July 15
<i>Geothlypis trichas sinuosa</i>	saltmarsh common yellowthroat	April 1 - July 31
<i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	loggerhead shrike	April 1 - May 31
<i>Laterallus jamaicensis coturniculus</i>	California black rail	Jan 15 - April 15
<i>Melospiza melodia maxillaris</i>	Suisun song sparrow	April 1 - May 31
<i>Rallus obsoletus obsoletus</i>	California Ridgway's rail	Jan 15 - April 15
<i>Sternula antillarum browni</i>	California least tern	April 1 - Aug 31
<i>Tyto alba</i>	barn owl	April 15 - July 15
<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	golden eagle	Jan 1 - Aug 31
<i>Agelaius tricolor</i>	tri-colored blackbird	Feb 15 - May 31
<i>Asio flammeus</i>	Short-eared owl	April 15 - July 15

The INRMP has identified five special-status mammal species that may occur at MOTCO, and are the subjects of focused survey efforts (Table 2). Two of these species, the SMHM and the saltmarsh wandering shrew (*Sorex vagrans halicoetes*), require conducting activities within the salt marsh for data collection and are proposed to occur from March through July.

Table 2. Special Status Mammal Surveys

Scientific Name	Common Name	Survey Period
<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Humpback whale	Summer
<i>Phoca vitulina richarii</i>	Pacific harbor seal	Mid to late June to coincide with low-low tide cycles under 1 foot.
<i>Reithrodontomys raviventris</i>	Salt marsh harvest mouse	March through July
<i>Sorex vagrans halicoetes</i>	Salt marsh wandering shrew	March through July
<i>Zalophus californianus</i>	California sea lion	May through July

A total of seven special-status plant species have been identified as targets of focused surveys within the INRMP (Table 3). Of these species, only soft bird's-beak is listed pursuant to the Act. This species is known to occur at MOTCO. Rare plant surveys may occur in areas that contain tidal marsh or sloughs.

Table 3. Rare Plant Surveys

Scientific Name	Common Name	Survey Period
<i>California macrophylla</i>	round-leaved filaree	March through May
<i>Chloropyron mollis</i> ssp. Mollis	soft bird's-beak	July through November
<i>Lathyrus jepsonii</i> var. <i>Jepsonii</i>	Delta tule pea	May through July
<i>Lilaeopsis masonii</i>	Mason's lilaeopsis	April through November
<i>Lilaeopsis masonii</i>	Delta mudwort	May through August
<i>Madia radiata</i>	showy madia	March through May
<i>Symphotrichum lentum</i>	Suisun marsh aster	May through November

The mapping of rare plants provides MOTCO with locations of sensitive resources where disturbance should be avoided, as well as where natural resources management efforts can be focused. MOTCO proposes to continue conducting rare plant surveys on an on-going basis. This effort will include survey events by qualified botanists during three flowering periods (May-July, and September). All rare plants identified, including soft bird's-beak will be mapped, and the size of the population will be estimated. These data will be provided to the Service on an annual basis.

- Design and Install Wildlife Information Signage

The installation of wildlife information signage is intended to be a conservation method to ensure sensitivity and awareness of special status species and habitat.

- Install Barricades to Limit Access to Special Status Species Habitat

The installation of barricades to limit access to biologically sensitive areas is intended to be a conservation method to ensure sensitivity and awareness of special status species and habitat.

Covered Activity 2: Wetland/Shoreline Management Programs and Projects

The dominant wetlands of the Tidal Area are the extensive tidal marshes, both on the mainland and the islands. The Wetland Preserve Area was first designated in a 1984 Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between the U.S. Navy and the Service, and the INRMP supersedes the former MOU. The INRMP outlines strategies for conservation of wetlands and the sensitive species that rely upon them. These include many of the tasks that are described in greater detail in other covered activities; studies and surveys of plants and wildlife, management of the Wetland Preserve to ensure conservation of essential functions and values, limitation on access, requirements for wetland delineation and species surveys prior to any proposed projects within potential wetlands, and close coordination with resources management agencies including the Service and NMFS.

- Wetland Delineation and Survey

Wetland delineation and survey requires that field biologists walk and map wetland features in the field.

- Design and Install Wetland Signage

The installation of wildlife information signage is intended to be a conservation method to ensure sensitivity and awareness of special status species and habitat.

- Install Barricades to Limit Access to Wetland Preserve Areas

The installation of barricades to limit access to biologically sensitive areas is intended to be a conservation method to ensure sensitivity and awareness of special status species.

Covered Activity 3: Invasive Plant Species Control Programs and Projects

The purpose of the invasive species management program is twofold: (1) to prevent the introduction and spread of invasive species; and (2) once they are detected, to control invasive species at MOTCO using the most effective biological, mechanical, or chemical means available. This program currently includes annually monitoring pesticide/herbicide applications on all leased lands and subsequently reviewing invasive species management plans from individual agriculture lessees. The annual review and subsequent approval of herbicide use is conducted by the Environmental Site Manager at MOTCO. This is to reduce the use of chemical means of weed control, per Department of Defense (DoD) Directive 4150.7.

Conducting invasive plant control is specifically intended to improve habitat quality and quantity for sensitive species at MOTCO.

- Invasive Species Surveys

To inform the INRMP's invasive species control and management program, a *Survey Plan for Rare and Invasive Plant Species, Marine Ocean Terminal Concord, California* was prepared in 2019 and addressed in the 2020 Habitat Sampling Plan (Vernadero 2019; Eco & Associates 2020). The invasive species survey plan identified target invasive plant species for management

within the BA coverage area, which have been the focus of surveys and mapping efforts conducted within the Tidal Area and Inland Area in 2019 and offshore islands in 2020 (Eco & Associates 2019 and 2021).

In cases where INRMP projects are proposed in salt marsh where CRR and SMHM may occur, surveying biologists will walk carefully through the marsh, avoiding high pickleweed cover and wrack where CRR are likely to nest or find cover.

- Invasive Species Management Including Use of Targeted Herbicides

Application of herbicides will be conducted using the practices and objectives outlined in the installation's 2022 Integrated Pest Management Program (IPMP).

The MOTCO Integrated Pest Management Coordinator (IPMC) periodically evaluates ongoing pest control operations and evaluates all new pest control operations against environmental documentation to ensure compliance with laws such as the Act, the Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act, the Clean Water Act, and the Migratory Bird Treaty Act. No pest management operations are proposed that are likely to have a negative effect on listed or protected species or their habitats without prior coordination with the MOTCO Environmental Office and approval from the Headquarters of the Army Material Command, and if required, reinitiation with the Service, NMFS, and/or approval from CDFW. This coordination could occur on an immediate as-needed basis or during the annual implementation meeting.

The IPMP for MOTCO is a comprehensive document using the principals of integrated pest management to control pest problems through the most economical and effective means of pest control. The plan describes the applicable policies, requirements, and major actions that affect the pest management program at MOTCO. Adherence to the plan will permit long range program planning with consistency in meeting regulatory requirements, and the best available control technology at the time of development. The MOTCO pest management program uses contracted pest controllers to control various categories of pests. The MOTCO IPMC/Pest Management Quality Assurance Evaluator oversees pest management operations. The MOTCO IPMC maintains daily records of pesticide applications, inspections, and nonchemical pest management operations on the installation. The records must account for all pest control operations and must provide a historical record of pest management operations and pesticide applications for each building, structure, or outdoor site. In addition, the records must include information on the kinds, amounts, uses, dates, and places of pesticide applications and applicator names and certification numbers.

Covered Activity 4: Wildlife Control Programs and Projects

- Installation of Wildlife Deterrence Measure and Exclusion Devices

The purpose of the cantonment area wildlife control program is to mechanically or chemically control rodents, insects, and other pests at MOTCO. The wildlife control program has a focus on humane, non-lethal methods to the extent practicable. The program requires surveys of buildings at the installation that are to be rehabilitated and re-used to determine if unwanted native wildlife species are gaining entrance through damaged walls, broken windows, or gaps in the roof eaves. MOTCO will then conduct repair of damage and/or installation of exclusion material (wood

panels, new window panes, heavy-duty galvanized meshing, etc.) to prevent further access by wildlife. Wildlife to be targeted include raccoon, opossum, skunk, rats, house mice, coyote, barn owl, dove, and bats. Where bird species are involved, work will be performed during the non-breeding season (generally, October through March) so as not to entrap native birds that may be nesting in buildings.

In addition to exclusion of wildlife from MOTCO buildings and facilities, MOTCO may utilize welded wire mesh as an exclusion method for California ground squirrels or other rodents. This is included as a part of the INRMP and may be combined with other INRMP projects such as removal of non-native vegetation efforts (i.e., iceplant). Welded mesh will be installed flush to the ground and is intended to avoid colonization of treated areas by making them unsuitable for burrowing animals.

MOTCO also intends to install raptor perches in order to provide predatory pressure to rodent populations. This effort includes placement of up to 25 raptor perches in Inland Areas away from suitable salt marsh harvest mouse and CRR habitat. Perches will be T-shaped and will utilize 16-foot-long, 4-inch-by-4-inch post, and a 4-foot-long, 4-inch-by-4-inch cross piece, with 2-inch-by-4-inch arms to support the cross piece. All wooden pieces will be made of treated lumber and bolted together using corrosion-resistant bolts.

Covered Activity 5: Water Quality and Erosion Control Programs and Projects

The purpose of water quality and erosion management is to minimize non-point source pollution and sediment laden runoff at MOTCO, which will help to protect the health and integrity of the entire watershed upstream, as well as the quality of the Tidal Area wetlands and the waters of Suisun Bay. Being part of a coastline ecosystem, MOTCO functions as a buffer between downstream flows from the Mount Diablo/Seal Creek basin and tidal flows of the San Francisco Bay-Delta estuary. Thus, the installation's tidal wetlands have an "opportunity" to perform such important functions as sediment stabilization, sediment/toxicant retention, nutrient removal/transformation, and production export. All of these functions are integral to managing and improving water quality, and trapping sediments before they erode into the bay. Many surface water features in the Tidal Area also function to recharge local groundwater zones. The primary goal of water quality management at MOTCO is to protect the health and quality of nearby water bodies (inland streams and the Bay's estuary) by reducing the likelihood of non-point source pollution. The primary goal of erosion control at MOTCO is to protect soil resources, to identify areas prone to soil erosion, and to prevent soil erosion and its subsequent impact on military facilities, water quality, and habitat values.

- Water Recharge and Rain Garden Projects

Projects under the Water Quality and Erosion Control Program are intended to be primarily focused on developed portions of MOTCO (existing and future). Typical projects are expected to include construction and rehabilitation of existing stormwater controls to direct stormwater to vegetated areas to the greatest extent practical, in order to promote groundwater recharge and to take advantage of naturally occurring filtration benefits. Such projects may include, for example, the daylighting of existing underground stormwater pipe systems into vegetated surface swales, or diversion of existing stormwater conveyance from underground pipework to rain gardens. These projects may include upgrades to stormwater controls for existing buildings, existing or

new parking lots, roadways, or other areas where opportunities may exist to upgrade stormwater recharge capacity. It is expected that the majority of such work will occur in developed or graded areas, it is likely that some of these projects will require some minor work at the point of discharge to existing local drainages; this may include installation of outfall structures, energy dissipation devices, or erosion control methods (such as rock slope protection).

- Stabilization of Stream Banks and Channels to Minimize Erosion

The INRMP has identified management goals to ensure minimization of erosion to existing stream banks and channels. These include the development of a monitoring program to include tracking of onsite creeks and drainages, monitoring of upslope areas for evidence of sloughing or sliding that may result in sediment movement, inspection of existing culverts, outfalls, and energy dissipators. The program also includes installation of erosion control measures where problems are found to exist; these may include typical BMPs such as erosion control fabrics or textiles, use of straw bales or tackifiers, as well as use of broadcast native seed as a method of stabilization. In areas where erosion is more severe, corrective measures may include placement of rock slope protection, planting of native tree species such as arroyo willow or other fast-growing riparian species, and minor corrective grading.

- Replacement, Repair, and Maintenance of Drainage Channels, Outfalls, Ditches, Retention Basins, Pond Dam Outfalls, Energy Dissipaters, Culverts, and Trash Capture Devices

Drainage channels, ditches, and associated components (termed 'water quality infrastructure' in this analysis) are generally man-made features. These facilities require maintenance and are cleaned periodically to permit unobstructed water flow and to avoid erosion and damage to roads, creek banks, and other infrastructure. Excavation of debris and sediment from ditches, channels, and detention or retention basins may require minor grading along ditches and at storm drain outfalls and inlets. Ditches and channels often require cleaning or grading when standing water is on a road shoulder or if deposits fill more than 50 percent of the capacity of the retention/detention basin. Retention or detention basins require periodic maintenance to preserve the line, grade, depth, and cross section to which they were originally designed.

Debris and accumulated sediment will be removed by manual cleaning methods or by using a backhoe or a vacuum truck. Solids will be disposed at an appropriate upland disposal facility, or recycled as fill material if suitable. Liquids may be decanted at an approved decanting facility such as an existing sediment basin or temporary basin constructed in an upland area. Equipment/vehicles required to complete these tasks may include pickup trucks, backhoes, vacuum trucks, hauling trucks, and hand-held tools such as shovels and rakes. The equipment generally operates from the nearest road or adjacent bank, although in rare instances equipment may be required to operate outside of these areas to clean difficult to reach drainage channels and ditches.

Culverts, box culverts, trash or debris capture devices attached to culverts, bridge piers, bridge abutments, and the adjacent stream channel will be cleaned of sediment and debris to provide sufficient depth and grade to ensure designed stream flow passes in the affected stream channel to prevent flooding concerns. Natural and anthropogenic debris will also be removed from bridge piers, and abutments. In some cases, it may be beneficial to retain stream sediments and woody

debris in the stream system and some or all of the material that is cleaned from the upstream inlet may be shifted and deposited in the channel downstream of the culvert or bridge.

Culverts, trash capture devices, basins, bridge structures or other infrastructure that are found to have been damaged by storm events, accumulated debris, or cleaning activities, may require replacement, repair, or retrofit. These structures may also be replaced in kind, repaired, or retrofitted to accommodate increased flow, sediment, trash capture needs or debris conditions. Culvert removal and replacement would be limited to ephemeral waterways outside of the rainy season when the channel is dry. Culvert replacements will include fish and wildlife passage design criteria, where applicable, to maintain, improve, or provide fish and wildlife passage and to ensure that the infrastructure continues to function in a safe and efficient manner. Large culverts may also be retrofitted with grade control structures such as rock, wood, or concrete weirs to provide or improve fish passage. Where wildlife passage and habitat connectivity improvements are needed, or where preventing wildlife-vehicle collisions is a priority, replacing a culvert may include installation of directional or exclusion fencing to funnel wildlife to cross under the roadway through the culvert or may include benching or shelving to provide dry areas for wildlife to walk on when water is flowing through the culvert.

- Installation of New Drainage Channels, Outfalls, Ditches, Retention Basins, Pond Dam Outfalls, Energy Dissipaters, Culverts, and Trash Capture Devices

In instances where MOTCO is proposing construction of new drainage channels, ditches, outfalls basins or associated infrastructure, these structures will be designed to include fish and wildlife passage design criteria, where applicable, to maintain, improve, or provide fish and wildlife passage and to ensure that the infrastructure continues to function in a safe and efficient manner. This task does not include projects that may propose realignment of existing drainage channels or creeks; it includes projects that may propose construction of new drainage channels in areas that are currently uplands and that may be utilized for drainage of upland areas at MOTCO. These drainage channels are most likely to be used in combination with water recharge and rain garden projects that may be associated with existing or new construction. Where wildlife passage and habitat connectivity improvements are needed, or where preventing wildlife-vehicle collisions is a priority, designs may include installation of directional or exclusion fencing to funnel wildlife to cross under a roadway through a culvert or may include benching or shelving to provide dry areas for wildlife to walk on when water is flowing through the culvert. All new infrastructure will be designed to accommodate expected flow parameters, accommodate wildlife passage concerns where they exist, and to provide for reasonable maintenance requirements following construction.

In cases where new infrastructure construction such as a new outfall structure may require temporary dewatering of an existing drainage feature, use of cofferdams may be employed, and slope protection or other erosion protection (including energy dissipaters) may be included in the design. In cases where construction activities must be isolated from the surrounding environment, such as when building cast in place concrete structures, use of coffer dams, plastic sheeting, and pumping of water from work areas to upland areas, may be required. Equipment/vehicles required to complete these tasks may include pickup trucks, backhoes, excavators, hauling trucks, and hand-held tools such as shovels and rakes. The equipment generally operates from the nearest road or adjacent bank, although in rare instances equipment

may be required to operate outside of these areas to clean difficult to reach drainage channels and ditches.

Covered Activity 6: Migratory Bird Management Programs and Projects

The goal of MOTCO's bird conservation efforts is to maintain fully functioning natural ecosystems that can provide for the needs of various and differing species. Maintaining ecological processes and the species that depend on them across landscapes that are intensively used by people is essential to planning.

MOTCO's *Final Migratory Bird Management Plan* outlines measures that includes monitoring, minimizing impacts, and creation of strategic partnerships to ensure conservation of migratory birds. The *Final Migratory Bird Management Plan* is provided in Appendix A-6 of the INRMP. Measures include specific reduction in pesticide use, and specific measures to conserve habitat required by migratory birds. It identifies management tools for on-site grassland areas including controlled burning, mowing, grazing, invasive vegetation reduction and management, and native vegetation restoration. It identifies tools for marsh management that include marsh protection, tidal flow restoration (where feasible), predator control, and installation of artificial nesting structures.

Implementation of the *Final Migratory Bird Management Plan* is specifically intended to improve habitat quality and quantity for migratory bird species at MOTCO. Field surveys require that field biologists identify and map locations of migratory birds in the field to complete bird inventories. This effort is intended to occur on an on-going and continued basis.

- Preconstruction Nesting Bird Surveys

Pre-construction bird surveys for work associated with covered activities may occur any time of the year depending on the INRMP project that is being implemented, but they are especially important during the spring and summer nesting seasons. These survey efforts are intended to focus on the area that may be affected by a specified project and the intent is to identify any conflicts that may occur in order to reduce or eliminate effects to nesting birds. These surveys will follow protocols by the Service, CDFW, or other existing sources, when such survey protocols exist. Typical nesting bird surveys include establishment of a survey area within a specified distance of a proposed project site (may be up to 0.5 mile for some raptors), and that surveys occur shortly before the start of the proposed project (within 10-14 days).

Covered Activity 7: Environmental Restoration Programs and Projects

Continuous military operations have taken place at the MOTCO site since the mid-1850s. Over this period, waste disposal practices deemed appropriate at the time, and accidental spills of hazardous substances during daily operations led to the contamination of soils and groundwater in several locations throughout the installation. The Navy implemented a Comprehensive Environmental Response Compensation and Liability Act (CERCLA) Information Repository (IR) program at Naval Weapon Station Seal Beach Detachment (NWSSBD) Concord in 1983 in order to collect and evaluate information in response to speculation that certain areas of the installation had contamination above acceptable levels. Responsibility for the continuation of the IR program for the Tidal and Inland Areas was transferred from the Navy to the Army with the

transfer of MOTCO on October 1, 2008. The Navy's IR efforts continue at the former NWSSBD Concord lands adjacent to the Inland Area. In addition to the IR program sites, there are three Military Munitions Response Program sites. The IR program includes a series of measures to remediate contamination including preliminary investigations, remedial design, and actions, followed (typically) by site monitoring.

The INRMP includes a total of 17 active remedial sites at MOTCO (See Table 4-1 in the INRMP). The majority of these sites are located within developed areas of MOTCO, however there are sites adjacent to tidal wetlands. These remediation projects are, by definition, actions to improve the overall and local environment, and in most cases, remediation projects subject to CERCLA are completed with individual section 7 consultation requests (on a per project basis). This activity is included in this document specifically because it is described in the INRMP, and efforts will be made in all cases to coordinate remediation projects with the goals described in the INRMP and the methods described in this document. Some initial site evaluation of potential contamination may be conducted under the umbrella of the INRMP. These activities may include initial site evaluation, soil sampling, or other data gathering exercises.

Scheduling, Sequencing, Staging, and Vegetation Removal

The covered activities for INRMP projects will occur throughout the year. Specific RMPs and SSPs will be identified at the beginning of each calendar year. A Service-approved project biologist will review proposed RMPs and SSPs and will prepare an Annual INRMP PBO Implementation Plan to address proposed actions within covered species habitat proposed for the calendar year. The plan will include the names and qualifications of proposed biological monitors. The approved biologist will evaluate the impacted covered species habitat within the proposed RMP/SSP work areas in regard to proposed construction schedule, activities, time of year, and potential effects. Sequencing and schedule of monitoring programs will be conducted according to Service protocol-level survey guidelines, while SSPs will be scheduled to the greatest extent practicable within applicable covered species work windows. SSP construction activities will take place primarily during day-time hours, with some night-time work. The general order of work for covered activity SSPs will involve pre-construction biological surveys and vegetation removal, establishment of staging areas, fencing installation, site preparation, construction, demobilization, and re-vegetation.

For SSPs involving vegetation clearing, a Service-approved biological monitor will be present onsite during vegetation removal to inspect for terrestrial species identified as requiring management consideration (Table 2-9 of the INRMP) and to verify that all clearing is done according to the conservation measures and permits. Vegetation clearing in advance of construction activities will be completed by use of hand tools, small mechanical tools, or heavy equipment from the roadway, but no heavy equipment access will be allowed in sensitive habitat areas, where practicable. The Army has determined that several listed species identified in Table 2-9 will not be affected by implementation of the INRMP and reinitiation may be appropriate if encountered during vegetation clearing.

Temporary staging areas will allow for equipment storage, equipment maintenance, and construction material storage during construction. These areas will be identified for each proposed SSP as part of the covered activities. Staging areas will be located in paved, gravel or non-friable soil areas not suitable for habitat to the greatest extent available. Materials containing

possible contaminants, such as fuels, lubricants, oils, or solvents, will be stored in appropriate containers at designated locations using the Caltrans standard contactor provisions, as this is the most appropriate standard for use at MOTCO.

SSP construction site preparation may include clearing and grubbing of vegetation, ground disturbing activities, construction of transportation structures, and dewatering/diversion. These activities will involve the greatest habitat impact as they include the use of heavy equipment. To reduce construction noise, the Army has elected to exclude impact pile driving as a method of sheet-pile and pipe-pile installation; however, auguring or vibratory pile installation can still affect the natural environment. Excavating, drilling, pouring concrete, and installing piles will take place during the proposed conservation work windows to the greatest extent practicable in each respective habitat type.

Conservation Measures

The Army is proposing to implement a number of general conservation measures such as standard BMPs, spill prevention plans, storm water pollution prevention plans, hazardous material management plans, and other general conservation measures. Please refer to the project BA and the INRMP for these BMPs. The following conservation measures are specific with regard to the SMHM and CRR.

Work will take place during species-specific work windows to the maximum extent practicable (Table 4). Work windows represent periods of time when direct impacts to listed species from activities conducted within their potential habitat are either completely avoided or minimal. For CLT, CTS, and CRLF, these species are not anticipated to be in the Action Area; however, as part of the purpose of the INRMP, the observation of work windows for these species are used for precaution. For CRR, the work windows include times outside of the breeding and nesting seasons. For SMHM, there are no work windows because these species may occur in the Action Area year-round and are not known to have sensitive life stages during certain times of year. Activities covered under the INRMP may occur throughout the year; however, outside of the work windows, certain activities that are determined at the time to have the potential to exceed or create an unanticipated adverse effect will either be prohibited in applicable habitats or specific avoidance and minimization measures will be implemented to minimize the potential for adverse effects.

Table 4. Work Windows

Species Habitat Type	Month of the Year											
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
CRLF					Work Window							
CTS					Work Window							
CLT	Work Window								Work Window			
CRR									Work Window			
SMHM					No Work Window							

General listed species measures:

1. A Service-approved biological monitor will conduct pre-construction surveys to inspect suitable habitat for listed species. If listed species are detected, the Service will be contacted and approved activities such as avoidance or relocation of listed species will be conducted. Once covered species have either determined to be absent or relocated to safety, fencing and/or flagging will be installed where and when appropriate. When appropriate, temporary, high-visibility fencing will delineate the project limits, staging areas, and temporary construction easements to exclude contractors from entering the sensitive habitat areas and discourage wildlife from entering construction areas. Temporary wetland and rare plant exclusion fencing is then installed when appropriate, under the supervision of the Service-approved biological monitor.
2. Prior to project-implementation, all construction personnel working on vegetation removal, earthmoving, and/or construction activities will attend a mandatory environmental education program, led by a Service-approved biologist. This program will include information regarding covered species occurring within the coverage area.
3. To minimize harassment, injury, mortality, and harm in the form of temporary habitat disturbances, all project-related vehicle traffic will be restricted to established roads, construction areas, equipment staging, parking, and stockpile areas. For SSPs in covered species habitat, the Army will limit the number of access routes, size of staging areas, and the total area of the activity to the minimum necessary to achieve the project goals. The Army will delineate Environmentally Sensitive Areas within covered species habitat to confine access routes and construction areas to the minimum area necessary to complete construction; this goal includes locating access routes and construction areas outside of listed species habitat to the maximum extent practicable.
4. SSP work areas conducted in listed species habitat will be delineated with orange wildlife exclusion fencing or flagging to minimize impacts to habitat beyond the work limit. Type of fencing or flagging will be defined in the Annual INRMP PBO Implementation Plan. A Service-approved biologist will supervise the installation of protective fencing. The fencing or flagging will be inspected by the Service-approved biologist immediately after installation and maintained daily by the project proponent until the last day that construction equipment is at the project. Orange cyclone fencing, materials that include nylon netting, or other materials that can entrap small amphibians and reptiles and other special-status species, will not be used.
5. SSP work areas in habitat for covered species will implement no-work buffers as defined in the Annual INRMP PBO Implementation Plan. Buffer distances will be site and species specific.
6. Vegetation will be removed for listed species observation as necessary prior to ground disturbance activity conducted within covered species habitat. The location and extent of vegetation removal will be defined in the Annual INRMP PBO Implementation Plan. Vegetation within ground disturbance areas will be removed using the least impacting method available just prior to the initiation of ground moving activities. A Service-

approved biologist will conduct a pre-construction survey within 48 hours prior to the start of any vegetation removal or SSP work activities or within covered species habitat. If a listed species is discovered during pre-construction surveys, the Service-approved biologist will notify the Army, who has the authority to stop all construction work on the site until the appropriate corrective measures have been conducted and it is determined that the animal will not be harmed.

7. A Service-approved biologist will monitor work associated with covered activities within listed species habitat. Monitoring location and frequency will be defined in the Annual INRMP PBO Implementation Plan. The Service-approved biologist will have the authority to stop any work that may result in adverse impacts to covered species. All listed species will be allowed to leave the site of their own accord.
8. For SSPs in habitat of terrestrial listed species, the biological monitor will check for animals under any equipment such as vehicles and stored pipes prior to commencement of work each day. In order to prevent inadvertent entrapment of these species during construction activities, all excavated, steep-walled holes or trenches more than 2 feet deep will be covered at the close of each working day by plywood or similar materials. Alternatively an additional 2-foot-high vertical barrier, independent of exclusionary fences, may be used to further prevent the inadvertent entrapment of these species. If it is not feasible to cover an excavation or provide an additional 2-foot-high vertical barrier, independent of exclusionary fences, one or more escape ramps constructed of earth fill or wooden planks will be installed. Before such holes or trenches are filled, they will be thoroughly inspected for trapped animals.
9. If nighttime work is required, work lights will be directed away from potential covered species habitat.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

1. In some instances, installation of exclusion fencing for SMHM may be necessary. Exclusion fencing will be installed at the discretion of the Service-approved biologist. All vegetation within potential habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse within the SSP work area and within a 2-foot buffer around the project footprint shall be removed by hand using only non-mechanized hand tools (i.e., trowel, hoe, rake, and shovel) prior to the initiation of work within these areas. Pickleweed stands will be removed by hand. Vegetation shall be removed to bare ground or stubble no higher than one inch. Vegetation shall be removed under the supervision of a Service-approved biologist. Vegetation removal may begin when no mice are observed and shall start at the edge farthest from the salt marsh or the poorest habitat and work its way towards better salt marsh habitat, and from center of project outward. Silt fences will be erected adjacent to construction areas to define and isolate potential mouse habitat. Temporary exclusion fencing shall be installed immediately after the hand removal of all vegetation from the work area and a 2-foot buffer around the work area. The fence shall be made of a heavy plastic sheeting material that does not allow SMHM to pass through or climb, and the bottom shall be buried to a depth of 4 inches so that SMHM cannot crawl under the fence. Fence height shall be at least 12 inches higher than the highest adjacent vegetation with a maximum height of 4 feet. All supports for the exclusion fencing shall be placed

on the inside of the work area. The Service-approved biologist will have the ability to make field adjustments to the location of the fencing depending on site-specific habitat conditions. Prior to the initiation of work each day, the person(s) designated by the Service-approved biologist shall thoroughly inspect the work area and adjacent habitat areas to determine if SMHM is present. Any necessary repairs to the exclusion fencing shall be completed within 24 hours of the initial observance of the damage. Work shall not continue within 300 feet of the damaged exclusion fencing until the fences are repaired.

2. No SSP work will occur within 50 feet of suitable tidal salt marsh habitat within two hours before and after an extreme high tide event (6.5 feet or higher measured at the Golden Gate Bridge and adjusted to the timing of local high tides) unless SMHM-proof exclusion fencing has been installed around the work area.
3. Prior to removal of vegetation for ground disturbance in SMHM habitat, a Service-approved biologist will inspect for signs of mice. Following inspection, personnel under the supervision of the qualified biologist, will disturb vegetation to encourage movement of individuals into adjacent marsh areas (i.e., flush).

California Ridgway's Rail

1. If CRR presence/absence surveys determine that breeding occurs within the coverage area, operation of construction equipment and other construction, maintenance or monitoring activities within or adjacent CRR habitat will be conducted to the extent practicable during the CRR work window of September 1 - January 31. Project activities may not exceed 80 decibels if conducted outside of the work window in areas found to have nesting CRR located within 700 feet of the project. If the surveys confirm there are no breeding rails within 700 feet of SSP work area limits, work can occur unimpeded outside of the CRR work window (i.e., during the breeding season of February 1 – August 31). If the intervening distance between the proposed project and the detected CRR location is across a substantial barrier between the CRR calling center or nest site, and any activity area is greater than 200 feet away, it may proceed at that location within the breeding season.
2. Work activities within or adjacent to suitable habitat will not occur within 2 hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above, as measured at the Golden Gate Bridge), when the marsh plain is inundated, because protective cover for CRR is limited and activities could prevent them from reaching available cover. If work is to occur in the breeding season that was determined from a lack of survey detections and a CRR nest is encountered during any project-related activity, the observers will immediately leave the vicinity of the nest. If CRR adults are encountered, observers will move away from the birds if they are giving alarm calls or otherwise appear alarmed.
3. Construction will be conducted outside of breeding season to the greatest extent practicable. However, should there be construction delays greater than 3 days during the CRR breeding season, or should construction be initiated during the breeding season, sound-attenuating blankets will be installed on the perimeter fencing between the project

and CRR rail habitat. Installation of the sound-attenuating blankets will reduce noise traveling to adjacent habitat areas.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” MOTCO is in the east San Francisco Bay region, approximately 10 miles inland past the Carquinez Strait, which connects Suisun Bay to San Pablo Bay. MOTCO consists of an approximately 115-acre Inland area and an approximately 6,526-acre Tidal Area, which includes 2,045 acres of offshore islands (Figure 1). The PBO coverage area encompasses the MOTCO boundary. The Inland area contains the majority of administrative offices on the installation. The larger area, referred to as the Tidal Area comprises the operational Tidal Area and seven offshore islands. This operational area includes approximately 5 miles of sinuous mainland shoreline; three ocean terminal piers and facilities for reception, staging, and loading of ammunition; railroad infrastructure; and the Los Medanos Hills. The offshore islands together consist of 2,045 acres and include the following seven islands and 205 acres of associated unnamed islands: Ryer Island (956 acres), Roe Island (280 acres), Freeman Island (127 acres), Snag Island (34 acres), East and West Seal Islands (27 acres total), and Middle Ground Island (416 acres). The Action Area includes approximately 3,100 acres of various tidal wetlands within MOTCO.

Figure 1.

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action but that are not part of the action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

California Ridgway’s Rail

Information about the California Ridgway’s rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the California

Ridgway's rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

MOTCO is a United States Army Military Surface Deployment and Distribution Command munitions and general cargo trans-shipment facility. The Inland Area has been disturbed by various developments over the years, but the overall physical geography has not been overly altered. However, the marsh areas of the Tidal Area have been extensively altered by diking, dumping, and filling since the 1800s. Most of the Tidal Area facilities are built on fills deposited in the marsh during original Navy construction. The Tidal Area lies on the southern edge of Suisun Bay, incorporating approximately 5 miles of shoreline. Extending from the tidal marsh upland edge are the Los Medanos Hills that form the eastern boundary of MOTCO, rising 626 feet above mean sea level. The shoreline of the MOTCO consists of riprap-protected slopes, a pile-supported wharf, dilapidated piers, and beach-fronted unprotected slopes. Aquatic habitats in the Action Area include open water habitat of Suisun Bay and associated tidal wetlands. Across Otter Slough to the west, Hastings Slough East Marsh is a matrix of fresh and saline emergent wetland, tidal marsh, and coastal scrub. Hastings Slough East Marsh receives ample tidal flow and is dominated by saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*), rushes (*Juncus* spp.), and sparscale (*Atriplex prostrata*).

All the upland areas within the Action Area can be categorized as developed, ruderal, and landscaped. Developed areas primarily consist of paved and compacted access roads, structures, or disturbed roadsides. Roadsides consist of ruderal ("weedy") vegetation, and bare ground is present in patches. These areas have been disturbed by human activities and are dominated by nonnative annual grasses and other ruderal species. Areas of urban lands are covered by at least 75 percent asphalt or buildings. The portion that is not covered by asphalt or buildings is normally composed of fill material.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Action Area includes approximately 3,100 acres of various tidal wetlands within MOTCO and is neighbored by approximately 760 acres of tidal marshes in the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area to the west and approximately 150 acres of tidal wetlands in the adjacent Bay Point Regional Shoreline to the east. Populations of SMHM were detected during the 1998-1999

surveys conducted by the University of Arizona (Downard *et al.* 1999) in several tidal marsh locations in and around MOTCO. These areas included Hastings Slough East Marsh. The population in Hastings Slough East Marsh is also documented in the California Natural Diversity Database (CNDDDB)(CDFW 2024). Two harvest mice, not identified to species, were encountered outside of the Action Area but within MOTCO property on August 1, 2018 and a nest with 3 or 4 blind and hairless young mice (not identified to species) were encountered on May 8, 2019 during construction activities under the May 5, 2017 consultation for *General Repairs of Bridges, Roads, and Utilities at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO)* (Service File Number 08FBDT00-2016-I-0226). Recent trapping surveys have documented SMHM in Hastings Marsh, Site 40, Pier Marsh, East Marsh, Roe Island, and Ryer Island (WRA Environmental Consultants 2022). With the historical occurrences of SMHM and more recent occurrences within the tidal marsh areas on MOTCO, it is reasonable to assume presence of SMHM in the tidal marsh within the Action Area.

California Ridgway's Rail

Historically, CRR have been documented in the Suisun Bay marshes and on MOTCO; however, no CRR has been detected on MOTCO in over 2 decades. During the 1998-1999 surveys in support of a previous INRMP (Downard *et al.* 1999), the CRR was found in the brackish habitat of Seal Creek Marsh, as well as within Hastings Slough East Marsh. During 2015 pre-construction surveys for MOTCO's Pier 3 Repairs Project, no CRR were observed and no vocalizations for the species were noted (H.T. Harvey 2014). In 2018 and 2020, CRR surveys were conducted in the Tidal Area and offshore islands; these surveys also did not detect any vocalizations for the species (Eco & Associates 2018 and 2021). Olofson Environmental Inc. recently conducted California Ridgeway rail and California black rail surveys between January and April 2024 and the report is pending. Sufficient tidal marsh habitat is available on MOTCO and in neighboring tidal marsh habitats that could support CRR and support recruitment.

Previous Consultations within or adjacent to the Action Area

The Service issued an informal concurrence letter for the Environmental Investigation at the Former Naval Weapons Station Seal Beach Detachment Concord Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2011-I-0313) to the Corps on the effects of the project on the threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*).

MOTCO prepared a ground squirrel management plan in 2012 which was the subject of a section 7 consultation between the Army and the Service. The Service concurred in a letter dated May 3, 2012, with the Army's determination that the Ground Squirrel Management Plan for MOTCO may affect, but would not likely adversely affect the CTS, CRLF, SMHM, CRR, or soft bird's-beak (Service File Number. 08ESMF00-2012-I-0186). Updates to the management plan were completed in 2021 with minimal changes that the Army determined did not require reinitiation.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Maintenance Dredging of the Suisun Bay Channel Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2013-F-0022) on June 20, 2013, to the Corps on the effects of the project on the delta smelt.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Remediation of the Department of the Army's Military Ocean Terminal, Concord's Sites 32 and 33 Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-

2013-F-0029) on February 21, 2014, with an amendment issued (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2013-F-0029-R001) on September 25, 2015, to the Army on the effects of the project on the delta smelt and its critical habitat, the SMHM, the CRR, and soft-bird's-beak.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Military Ocean Terminal Concord Military Munitions Response Program Remedial Investigation and Feasibility Study (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2013-F-0040) on April 15, 2014, to the Army for effects of the project on the SMHM, the CRR, and soft-bird's-beak.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Modernization and Repair of Piers 2 and 3 at Military Ocean Terminal Concord (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2014-F-0002-5) on February 4, 2015, to the Army for effects of the project on the delta smelt and its critical habitat, the SMHM, the CRR, the CRLF, and soft bird's-beak.

The Service issued an informal concurrence letter for the MOTCO Barge Pier Fender Replacement Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2015-I-0029) on August 4, 2015, to the Army for effect of the project on the delta smelt and its critical habitat.

The Service issued an informal concurrence letter for the General Repairs of Bridges, Roads, and Utilities at Military Ocean Terminal Concord Project (Service File Number 08FBDT00-2016-I-0226) on May 5, 2017, to the Army on the effects of the project on the SMHM, the CRR, the CLT, and soft bird's-beak.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Proposed Maintenance Dredging at Military Ocean Terminal Concord Project (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0010) on December 30, 2019, to the Army with a reinitiation issued (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0010-R001) on December 13, 2021, for effects to the delta smelt and its critical habitat, and the SMHM.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Routine Maintenance and Repair Activities on Military Ocean Terminal Concord (Service File Number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0018) on June 22, 2020, to the Army for effects of the project on the delta smelt and the SMHM.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Construction, Operation, and Maintenance of a Loading/Unloading Ramp at Military Ocean Terminal Concord Project (Service File Number: 2022-0000493-S7-001) on July 21, 2022, to the Army for effects of the project on the delta smelt, the SMHM, and the CRR.

The Service issued a biological opinion on the Federal Aviation Administration Removal of Auxiliary Building, Antenna, and Fencing in Military Ocean Terminal Concord Project (Service File Number: 2022-0014966-S7-001) on September 16, 2022, to the Federal Aviation Administration for effects of the project on the SMHM.

Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action, but that are not part of the action. A consequence is caused by the proposed

action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. *Effects of the Action* may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse and California Ridgway's Rail

Covered Activity 1: Special Status Species Programs, Covered Activity 4: Wildlife Control Programs and Projects, Covered Activity 5: Water Quality and Erosion Control Programs and Projects, Covered Activity 6: Migratory Bird Management Programs and Projects, and Covered Activity 7: Environmental Restoration Programs and Projects.

Implementation of these programs are necessary to achieve the resource management goals of the INRMP. Certain special status species monitoring protocols and construction projects associated with erosion control and restoration may include equipment noises, vibration, sound and visual disturbance that may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual SMHM and CRR to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover and could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. The Army proposes to avoid the breeding season for the CRR (February 1 - August 31) for certain activities which will avoid the potential for adverse effects to their reproduction. This measure reduces, but does not eliminate the potential for adverse effects to the CRR and may not be sufficient to reduce impacts in areas where CRR are present. The Army also proposes to implement several conservation measures for the SMHM which include worker education, a Service-approved biologist on site during activities such as vegetation removal, preconstruction surveys, and exclusion fencing. These measures reduce, but do not eliminate the potential for adverse effects to the SMHM and may not be sufficient to reduce impacts in areas where SMHM are present.

The installation of signage is not expected to result in any direct effects to listed species; however, the sound generated by installation of signage near CRR nesting habitat could also result in nest abandonment or behavioral disturbance. This could only occur for activities conducted near or adjacent to tidal marsh, or wetland sloughs, where CRR are assumed to exist.

Covered Activity 2: Wetland/Shoreline Management Programs and Projects

The presence of biologists in the field and sound generated by installation of barriers may result in indirect disturbance to SMHM and CRR in the form of behavioral modification if wetland delineation and barrier installation efforts are conducted in areas where the species is present. These activities could also result in nest abandonment or behavioral modification if they occurred where CRR were nesting.

Covered Activity 3: Invasive Species Control Programs and Projects

Field surveys require that field biologists walk and map locations of invasive plants and populations in the field for target removal. The presence of biologists in the field may result in indirect disturbance to SMHM and CRR in the form of behavioral modification if this mapping occurs within tidal marsh or wetland sloughs where these species are present. In addition, some herbicides may cause adverse effects in the form of irritation to skin, eyes, digestive, and/or

nervous systems to these species if they were to come into direct contact or ingest during foraging. Herbicides used in invasive plant controls could have residual effects on nearby native plant populations that could reduce or diminish food sources for the SMHM and CRR at the source of application. This is anticipated to be minimized or negligible based on the size of available salt marsh habitats for the SMHM and the CRR in and around MOTCO and the application of herbicides and conservation measures described in the IPMP that are reasonably expected to minimize these effects. Because the Army proposes to utilize rodenticides in the IPMP, there is potential that a SMHM could be killed through poisoning. This is anticipated to be avoidable as the application of rodenticides for ground squirrel control and other mammalian pests outside of marsh habitat along with the appropriate conservation measures described in the IPMP are reasonably expected to avoid injuring or killing a SMHM.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline*, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that covered activities proposed under the Army's MOTCO 2023-2028 INRMP are not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the SMHM or the CRR. This is based on the current status and distribution of the SMHM and the CRR populations range-wide as analyzed in the species' most recent 5-year reviews and additional recent population/distribution data available to the Service, and the implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual SMHM, CRR, and their habitats during construction activities.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3). Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Army so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Army has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Army (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Army must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(4)].

Amount or Extent of Take

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse and California Ridgway's Rail

The Service anticipates incidental take of SMHM and CRR will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), a surrogate for individual animals may be used to express the amount or extent of anticipated incidental take if the biological opinion or Incidental Take Statement (ITS). Surrogates are used for this ITS because it is difficult to accurately quantify and monitor the amount or number of individuals that are expected to be incidentally taken as a result of the proposed action. Therefore, the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual SMHM and CRR. The Service anticipates incidental take of all SMHM and CRR within the entirety of tidal marsh habitats within MOTCO in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the covered activities such as survey efforts and other similar activities conducted in or near the 3,100 acres of tidal marsh habitats. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act. The Service does not anticipate that take in the form of wounding or killing of SMHM or CRR will occur due to the intended nature of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service is not exempting take in the form of wound or kill for any SMHM or CRR during construction activities from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the SMHM or the CRR.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the SMHM and CRR resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize incidental take of the SMHM and CRR:

1. All *Conservation Measures*, as described in the biological assessment and restated here in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this programmatic biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Term and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Army shall ensure that its contractors comply with the following term and condition, which implement its respective reasonable and prudent measure described above. This term and condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Army shall implement the *Conservation Measures* as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* and comply with this biological opinion.
 - b. The Army shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and *Term and Condition* in this biological opinion.
 - c. The Army shall ensure its contractors comply with the *Reporting Requirements* below.
 - d. The Army shall include the Service's San Francisco BDFWO in annual INRMP meetings with the Service's SFWO.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Army shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Army must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Army shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/BIOS>).
3. The Army will provide a list of activities annually that are covered and implemented under this PBO annually to the Service.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic

bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes programmatic formal consultation for the Department of the Army's Military Ocean Terminal Concord Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan, Programs, and Projects, Contra Costa County, California. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Senior Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2022-0070999-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

- (CDFW) California Department of Fish and Wildlife. 2018. Protocols for Surveying and Evaluating Impact to Special-Status Native Plant Populations and Sensitive Natural Communities. March 2018.
- _____. 2024. California Natural Diversity Database. Biogeographic Data Branch, Sacramento, CA. Accessed at <https://apps.wildlife.ca.gov/bios/> April 1, 2024.
- (CNPS) California Native Plant Society. 2001. California Native Plant Society's Inventory of Rare and Endangered Plants of California. Sixth Edition. August 2001.
- Downard, G.T., P. Guertin, and M. Morrison. 1999. Characterization of wildlife and plant communities for Naval Weapons Station Seal Beach Detachment Concord. July 1998 to September 1999 results. Prepared for Department of Navy, Natural Resource Management Branch, Engineering Field Activity West, San Bruno, CA.
- Eco & Associates. 2018. June 2018 – Environmental Surveys for Military Ocean Terminal Concord (MOTCO), Concord, California. Prepared for the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers by ECO & Associates, Inc. June 2018.
- _____. 2019. Rare and Invasive Plant Mapping Survey Report, Military Ocean Terminal Concord, California. Prepared for the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers by ECO & Associates, Inc. November 2021.
- _____. 2020. Final Habitat Sampling Plan, Conservation Services, Military Ocean Terminal Concord. Prepared for the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers by ECO & Associates, Inc. and Vernadero Group, Inc. January 2020.
- _____. 2021. Draft Annual Report, Conservation Services, Military Ocean Terminal Concord Contra Costa County, California. Prepared for the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers by ECO & Associates, Inc. and Vernadero Group, Inc. February 2021.
- H.T. Harvey and Associates. 2014. California Clapper Rail Survey Results Military Ocean Terminal Concord Modernization of Piers 2 and 3 Concord, California, April 17, 2014.
- (Service) U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2000. Guidelines for Conducting and Reporting Botanical Inventories for Federally Listed, Proposed and Candidate Plants. January 2000.
- _____. 2013. Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California. Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. xviii + 605 pp. https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf
- _____. 2020. 5-YEAR REVIEW: California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). San Francisco Bay-Delta Office, Sacramento, California. 33 pp. https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf

_____. 2021. 5-YEAR REVIEW: Salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. 29 pp.
https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3630.pdf

Vernadero Group Inc. (Vernadero). 2019. Survey Plan for Rare and Invasive Plant Species, Marine Ocean Terminal Concord, California. January.

WRA Environmental Consultants. 2022. Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Survey Results Military Ocean Terminal Concord. Concord, Contra Costa County, California. October 2022.